

Double Degree M.Sc Program on Industrial Safety Engineering with Aerospace Application: A Case Study

O. Ivanova^{1,2}, M. Ivanov¹, M. Kuznetsov¹, A. Aleksandrov¹, R. Revetria²

¹ Bauman Moscow State Technical University, Moscow, Russia

² University of Genoa, Genoa, Italy

Email: olgaivanova@bmstu.ru

Abstract

The paper describes an experience of Bauman Moscow State Technical University (Russia) and University of Genoa (Italy) in design and implementation of a double degree M.Sc. program “Master in Industrial Safety Engineering” with its application to the aerospace industry. Preparatory phase, elaboration of the double curricula, students’ enrolment and transfer of records and award of the diploma is presented in the paper. The application to the aerospace has been carried out by introducing research topics related to space exploration. An example of such topic is provided. Results of the double degree implementation have demonstrated its efficiency and usefulness. Students show high interest to the program and study hard in order to obtain two diplomas.

Keywords: Double degree, case study, curricula.

1 Introduction

Today in the era of globalization, internationalization and World-wide reforms universities, which often used to find themselves competing against one another in a struggle to attract students, donors, best talents and best research resources, are now seeking partnerships outside their country borders in order to meet the challenges and opportunities that internationalization and Europeanization of higher education offers. (van der Ploeg and Veugelers, 2008 and Lyapunsova et al., 2020). Cooperation is always more fruitful than competition. However, the aerospace industry was traditionally considered one of the most conservative and classified. This resulted in additional difficulties in establishment of a collaboration of any kind between different countries (Levinzon, Suleyman, Tsarkova, 2019 and Briano, Catania, Revetria, 2008). Among different types of university partnerships one can distinguish participation in associations, academic mobility of students and staff. Of the most complicated and advanced form of such collaboration is students’ education performed by two or more universities simultaneously.

Such partnership programs may be generally divided into two types: double degree programs and joint degree programs (Johnstone et al. 1998 and Lyapunsova et al. 2019).

Joint degree program assumes study of the students at both universities simultaneously and ends up with awarding of a single diploma with signatures and stamps of all universities who were delivering studies (Carnoy, 2000). Although this is the most advanced type of study program it can’t often be realized in many countries of the World including Russia as it requires changes in national higher education regulations (Tatarinov, 2019 and Drobyshev et al., 2019).

Double degree programs deliver studies by all participating universities in a consecutive way, students’ study firstly in one university and then move to another. All records achieved in the partner universities have to be transferred to their home universities according to the regulations established between the universities. The studies end up with award of several diplomas: one per each partnering university. In this case study program in each university may slightly change and adapt to the local regulations. This makes it much simpler in many cases to award the degree and perform studies. Furthermore, after graduation students obtain several diplomas of higher education at once.

Thus, the double degree program was chosen as it was considered by us as more applicable and easily implemented.

2 Description of the Double Degree Program

The study program has been developed together by the department of Ecology and Industrial Safety of Bauman Moscow State Technical University (BMSTU) in Moscow, Russia and Department of Mechanical and Electronical Engineering at University of Genoa (UNIGE) in Genoa, Italy. Bauman Moscow State Technical University is well known for its aerospace developments and researches. University of Genoa also performs a lot of studies applied for aerospace. Furthermore, both universities have found that the topic of industrial safety may be considered as the most versatile and advanced. Also, a positive experience of invited lectures UNIGE professors at BMSTU was used as a good basement for double degree establishment.

In 2017 a cooperation agreement between BMSTU and UNIGE has been signed on development of a double degree program “Master in industrial Safety - MISE”. This agreement has considered all the issues that may occur during program implementation. These are selection and enrolment of students, ensuring student mobility among both universities, ensuring teachers exchange, approval of the rights of the students in each university, preparation and defense of the master thesis, award of the certificates and diplomas, actions in case of students’ academic failures, issues related to financial and general management of the activity and other minor issues. Last but not the least the cooperation agreement introduced the selection criteria admission and study program itself.

General flow of the students is presented at Figure 1.

Figure 1. General student academic mobility at MISE program.

It fixes two mobility plans: from the students originally of BMSTU and originally of UNIGE. Both groups start studies in September (beginning of the term) and end in June (end of the term). The thesis defense always is done in the home institution. This means, that originally BMSTU students stay and study at UNIGE from September to June of the first year. In July they move to their home institution and end their studies there. UNIGE students, on the other hand, spend their first year at their home institution and move to BMSTU only in the beginning of September. They stay there until May-June and then come back to Italy to do the thesis defense.

It is important to mention that both participating universities have already had similar programs taught in their native languages: Master in Analysis and Management of Natural and Human-related risks (Area of Specialization 20.04.01 Safety in Technosphere) in BMSTU and Laurea Magistrale in Safety Engineering for Transport, Logistics, and Production classe LM26 in UNIGE. Therefore, contents for many courses has been already prepared. After comparison of the programs it was concluded that among courses that may be

recognized equally by both universities, however, there are some courses that are delivered only in one of the participating universities (Table 1.).

Subjects in Table 1 are recognized by both universities if they are allocated in front of each other and not marked with any color. Otherwise, the subjects are delivered only by one university, i.e. Technologies for safety, security, and infomobility and Theory and Analysis of transport systems are delivered only in UNIGE and Methodology of scientific research and Dynamic risk analysis are delivered only in BMSTU. This means that two programs combined in any case would have a higher workload than individually. This would require more study time from students, higher motivation and exceptional skills.

In order to perform correct recognition of the studies a table of grades equivalence was elaborated. It is presented in Table 2. Subjects that considered to be equal are located in front of each other.

Table 1. Comparison of the study programs of UNIGE and BMSTU.

UNIGE		BMSTU	
Nº	Subject	Nº	Subject
5.1.	Technologies for safety, security, and infomobility		
3.1.	Theory and Analysis of transport systems		
3.2.	Planning and design of transport systems		
4.2.	European Union Law and Transport Policy		
5.2.	Telecommunications networks		
7.1.	Safety and security of transport systems		
7.2.	Integrated and sustainable transport systems		
		B3.	Methodology of scientific research
		10	Dynamic risk analysis
		12	Economics of environment safety
		E17	Applied methods of natural and man-made emergencies risk analysis
		Pr19	Pedagogical practicum
6.2.	Production quality and sustainability	9	Theory of risk analysis and management
9.	Industrial Logistics	E14	Risk and reliability of technical systems
		Pr23	Risk and reliability - Coursework
8.	Energy systems and environmental impact	11	Heat-mass exchange in biosphere
6.1.	Principles of industrial safety Engineering	B4.	Environment Safety Inspection
		Pr24	Environment safety inspection - Coursework
10.1.	Technologies for goods safety and security	6	Technosphere safety management
2.2.	Modelling and control of traffic systems	8	Mathematical modelling
E1.	Environmental mitigation strategies in coastal areas	E15	Risk analysis in case of emergencies in coastal areas

		B2.	Foreign language
E3.	Methods and models for decision support	B1.	System analysis and processes modelling in technosphere
		Pr25	Risk analysis and management - Courseproject
10.2.	Supply chain resiliency	7	GIS-technologies for risk analysis at hazardous objects
1.	Data analysis and mining	E13	Experimental planning and postprocessing
4.1.	Safety Engineering law	E16	State policy in risk management
2.1.	Optimisation and control methods	B5.	Control systems in technics
11.	Seminars and orientation	Pr21	Industrial practicum (4 weeks after 2 semester)
		Pr22	Prediploma practicum
		Pr18	Research
12.	Final exam	26	Final exam

Each successfully completed course is estimated in certain amount of ECTS credits. Students must acquire at least 30 ECTS credits in the home University and at least 30 ECTS credits of taught modules at the hosting University.

After all agreements have been made and all legal documents prepared the double degree program was initiated.

Table 2. Grades equivalence.

Grade	Scale		
	BMSTU	UNIGE	
Excellent cum laude	5+	30 cum laude	
Excellent	5	24-30	
Good	4	21-23	
Satisfactory	3	18-20	
Poor	2	0-17	
Pass	Pass	Pass	18-30
Fail	Fail	Fail	0-17
Did not attend	NA	Did not attend	DNA

3 Implementation of the Double Degree Program

After the study programme has been approved jointly by both institutions, a committee has been assigned to manage programme implementation. The committee consisted of members of both universities. The committee did selection of the students for first intake and managed their enrolment and further study process. First intake of the students was launched in September 2017. Three students from BMSTU and three students from UNIGE were enrolled to the program (Buldakova and Mikov, 2019 and Tatarinov et. al., 2019). First year of study was carried out in UNIGE according to the study plan. Russian students were allocated in UNIGE dormitories and provided with all relevant societal security.

All studies were done fully in English. To do this all study materials were translated into English and a series of study books were prepared. When possible, existing English literature was used.

After completion of the first-year students have moved to BMSTU, where they were also provided with the university dormitories and national social security.

Jointly by both universities it was decided that the MISE program will have an aerospace specialization. This was realized by introducing research topics related to ensuring human safety in space and space development projects. In example, one of the students' research projects was dedicated to safety design principles applied to a new manned reentry vehicle from space. This project reviews the study of the design and development of a Clipper landing vehicle.

This has been studied first in the last decade of the XX century as a new way to reach Space and to come back with a new technology which would have been reliable and reusable for at least forty years.

This analysis has been done to define the optimal characteristics with data and hypotheses found during the literature research with particular attention to the safety concepts and on the environmental impact of the facilities involved in the program.

After a theoretical analysis, with the support of programs such as Mathcad 15.0 ©, Autodesk® Inventor® Professional 2017 and SLAB, different considerations brought to the choice of which model of Clipper would be the best, among the configurations considered. Then how to develop the landing system and which rocket would be the most adapt in achieving a successful departure and return from Space.

In June-July 2019 all students have successfully completed and defended their theses in front of an academic board of their home institution. Partner institution was participating in the defense in person when the defense was in BMSTU or by means of remote internet connection when the defense was in UNIGE (Figure 2).

All students of the first intake obtained highest grades and were awarded with M.Sc diplomas cum laude of both universities.

The results of programme implementation were assessed by a committee consisting of members of both institutions. The committee agreed that project may be assessed as successful and should be repeated for the next intake. In September 2019 a second intake of students was launched. Three students from BMSTU have been sent for first year of studies to UNIGE.

Figure 2. A remote connection for participation in final thesis defense at UNIGE.

4 Conclusion

As result it may be considered that MISE double degree program may be considered as a successful and useful experience. However, there were some difficulties in providing a scholarship to the students on the period of staying abroad; lack of free space in the dormitories; general decline of the teaching quality due to transition to non-native English language.

Nevertheless, students gain much broader knowledge that is provided by different universities in different countries; English language should not be considered as the main difficulty in teaching; 6 students in two years of studies have published 17 articles in Scopus journals.

5 References

- van der Ploeg, Frederick, and Reinhilde Veugelers. "Towards evidence-based reform of European universities." *CESifo Economic Studies* 54.2 (2008): 99-120.
- Lyapunsova, E. V., Belozerova, I. M., Borkovskaya, V. G., Drozdova, I. I., & Baranova, Y. S. Organization and Management of Educational Work in Universities in the Light of National Strategic Guidelines for the Development of Education IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, Volume 459, Chapter 5 (2020).
- Levinzon, Suleyman V., and Natalia V. Tsarkova. "Criteria for evaluating the technical universities of the world using Forbes rating." 2019 54th International Universities Power Engineering Conference (UPEC). IEEE, 2019.
- Briano, Enrico, Alessandro Catania, and Roberto Revetria. "e-learning: analysis development and opportunities of the new way of teaching in Italy." *Proceedings of the Seventh IASTED International Conference*. Vol. 610. 2008.
- Johnstone, Donald Bruce, Alka Arora, and William Experton. *The financing and management of higher education: A status report on worldwide reforms*. World Bank, Human Development Network, Education, 1998.
- L Lyapunsova, E. V., Vdovichenko, M., Belozerova, Y., & Gorbатов, A. (2019, December). Application of modern modeling methods: virtual technologies in the era of digitalization and their role in modern companies. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1425, No. 1, p. 012165). IOP Publishing..
- Carnoy, Martin. "Globalization and educational reform." *Globalization and education: Integration and contestation across cultures* (2000): 43-61.
- Tatarinov, V. V. "Methods of teaching fundamental disciplines to foreign students at Bauman Moscow State Technical University by the example of mathematics." *AIP Conference Proceedings*. Vol. 2195. No. 1. AIP Publishing LLC, 2019.
- Drobyshev, D. V., K. A. Neusypin, and T. Yu Tsibizova. "Distance education in the training system of highly qualified personnel." *AIP Conference Proceedings*. Vol. 2195. No. 1. AIP Publishing LLC, 2019.
- Buldakova, T. I., and D. A. Mikov. "Matlab application for information security risk analysis." *AIP Conference Proceedings*. Vol. 2195. No. 1. AIP Publishing LLC, 2019.
- Tatarinov, V. V., U. V. Prus, and A. A. Kirsanov. "Decision support software for chemical accident elimination management." *AIP Conference Proceedings*. Vol. 2195. No. 1. AIP Publishing LLC, 2019. M., & de Graaff, E. (2017). The philosophical and pedagogical underpinnings of Active Learning in Engineering Education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 42(1), 5-16.